

YOLOv8-Based Architecture for Pose Estimation of Uncooperative Spacecraft

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Achieving autonomous spacecraft operations is crucial for missions such as On-Orbit Servicing (OOS) and Active Debris Removal (ADR). In this frame, this work focuses on visual-based relative navigation by introducing a pose estimation architecture relying on the combination of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with state-of-the-art Perspective-n-Points (PnP) solvers. Specifically, a two-stage deep learning approach is proposed: in the first stage, a YOLOv8-based network effectively localizes the target allowing the selection of a region of interest; the second stage employs a specialized YOLOv8-pose network to detect and identify a set of 2D points on the image plane corresponding to natural features of the target's surface by solving a regression problem. The resulting set of 2D-3D point correspondences is input to an analytical PnP solver followed by a first pose refinement step relying on the numerical solution of a least-squares problem through Gauss-Newton method and a subsequent additional refinement based on the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. Performance assessment is carried out by training and testing the CNNs and the entire processing pipeline on the SPEED+ dataset getting a mean rotation of 1.37° and a mean translation error of 4.7 cm.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the high number of satellites in orbit has strongly increased the demand for OOS and ADR missions [1] [2]. The success of autonomous proximity operations conducted by a chaser spacecraft in these scenarios requires real-time estimation of its position and orientation (i.e., pose) with respect to the target spacecraft [3] [4]. To this aim, increasing attention is placed on using monocular cameras given their low size, weight, and power requirements. Monocular-based pose estimation is a complex task especially if the target is non-cooperative. Traditional methods require the detection and matching of 2D image features followed by the solution of the resulting PnP problem [5]. However, they still experience a

lack of accuracy and robustness against the large variability of pose and illumination conditions, as well as the presence of cluttered image background [6]. In recent years deep learning (DL) has gained significant success in object recognition and detection, leading to its gradual application in object 6D pose estimation [7], while the results of ESA's Spacecraft Pose Estimation Challenges [8] [9] have shown that DL-based methods represent a promising approach also for non-cooperative space scenarios. DL-based spacecraft pose estimation algorithms make extensive use of CNNs and they can be broadly classified into direct [10–15] or hybrid [16–18] approaches depending on whether they output the pose or a set of identified features (thus requiring the subsequent solution of a PnP problem). A vast and growing body of literature exists demonstrating the feasibility of both approaches. However, the analysis of the top-10 methods from the first edition of the ESA Kelvin Satellite Pose Estimation Challenge (KSPEC'19) [19] indicates that the hybrid approaches perform better than the direct approaches. This result is also confirmed by the second edition of the same challenge (KSPEC'21) [9]. Still the results presented by literature works show room for improvement both in terms of accuracy and robustness. The top-performing algorithms demonstrate the advantage of optimizing accuracy for pose estimation. However, they also exhibit disadvantages such as high parameter count, which necessitates substantial computational resources, and extended inference time. In this context, this work presents an innovative and lightweight hybrid architecture for monocular-based uncooperative pose estimation, exploiting two state-of-the-art CNNs, one for target detection and the other for keypoints extraction and identification. Specifically, such tasks are performed by the YOLOv8n and YOLOv8s-pose networks which maintain an optimal balance between accuracy and the number of parameters, becoming ideal for real-time applications; successively, the Efficient PnP (EPnP) algorithm is employed to retrieve a coarse pose solution which is first refined

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using a Gauss-Newton least squares solver, then it is further corrected with Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm [20]. The SPEED+ dataset [21] containing synthetic images of the Tango satellite has been used for training, validation, and testing of the CNNs composing the proposed architecture. The rest of the paper presents the proposed methodology in Section 2, describes the achieved results in Section 3, and provides conclusions and indications of future works in Section 4.

2 Methodology

The pose estimation pipeline, depicted in Figure 1, consists of three main modules: an Object Detection Network (ODN) is utilized to predict the 2D rectangular bounding box of the satellite in the acquired image. The cropped image is then fed to a Keypoints Regression Network (KRN) to forecast the position of the keypoints in the image. Finally, since the keypoints coordinates in the target reference frame (TRF) are known [21], the predicted 2D-3D correspondences are input to a Pose solver block including an analytical coarse solver (EPnP) followed by Gauss-Newton refinement and a subsequent numerical refinement (LM algorithm).

2.1 Object Detection Network

The pipeline starts by detecting the bounding box containing the target in the image; this step enhances the possibility of correctly detecting the features in the successive step of the algorithm, despite the potential presence of the Earth in the background. To train the ODN, it is necessary to construct the satellite bounding boxes for each image composing the dataset. These 2D bounding boxes were obtained by projecting the 3D extreme coordinates of the target satellite onto the image using the ground-truth relative position vectors and relative attitude quaternions. The rectangular bounding box is therefore determined by considering the extreme coordinates of the reprojected points on the image plane. To ensure that no keypoint will be located on the border of the bounding boxes, thus compromising its detection through the successive keypoints' regression network, the boxes were enlarged by 2% of the maximum between the length and the height with respect to the computed box. Target detection relies on the YOLOv8 network, and specifically on its lightest version, YOLOv8-nano (YOLOv8n), which is particularly suitable for real-time applications due to the relatively low number of parameters, i.e., 3.2 million [22]. This network uses a multiscale ODN that does not require predefined an-

chor box sizes, thereby improving the efficiency and accuracy of the detection. This is designed to detect objects at various scales within the image, dynamically adapting to the sizes and features of the objects. The loss function used to train this detection network consists of three main components. The first is a localization term based on Complete Intersection over Union (CIoU), which measures how well the predicted bounding box overlaps with the ground-truth bounding box, taking both central distance, dimension congruence, and aspect ratio into account. The second term is dedicated to the classification of detected objects, ensuring that each object is correctly identified. Lastly, the loss function includes a term called Distribution Focal Loss (DFL), which further improves detection accuracy by promoting high classification scores for the predicted boxes close to the true bounding box [23]. Therefore, the total loss function is a weighted sum of the three terms,

$$L_{\text{tot}} = w_{\text{CIoU}}L_{\text{CIoU}} + w_{\text{class}}L_{\text{class}} + w_{\text{DFL}}L_{\text{DFL}} \quad (1)$$

where the weighting coefficients $w_{\text{CIoU}}, w_{\text{class}}, w_{\text{DFL}}$ are set to 7.5, 0.5 and 1.5, respectively. The choice of this one-stage detection network is driven not only by the low computational complexity, but also by the high performance achieved in target detection tasks [24]. Since only one target is expected to be found in such monocular images, in case of multiple detections, which may be due to inaccuracies in the target detection task, only the box corresponding to the largest confidence score is selected for the successive step. Therefore, the output of the network is employed to crop the image around the expected position of the target, which is fed to the keypoints' regression network.

2.2 Keypoints Regression Network and Pose Determination

The objective of the keypoints' regression network is to determine the position of some natural keypoints on the target, such as corners or appendages, within the cropped images around the bounding box obtained by the ODN. To this aim, the YOLOv8-pose network, in its small version (YOLOv8s-pose) is utilized, with approximately 11.6 million parameters [22]. The network presents a similar architecture to the YOLOv8 network, with additional convolutional layers in the detection head which enable keypoints' identification. To this aim, the loss function is enriched with an additional term related to the Euclidean distance between the expected and actual position of the keypoints; the total loss function is defined

Figure 1: Overall architecture of our satellite pose estimator.

by the following weighted sum,

$$L_{tot} = w_{CIoU}L_{CIoU} + w_{class}L_{class} + w_{DFL}L_{DFL} + w_{key}L_{key} \tag{2}$$

where the weight w_{key} of the keypoint loss is set to 12 to ensure training focus on the keypoints regression task. The network can be employed to detect both visible and not visible keypoints, e.g., points which are in the field of view (FOV) of the monocular sensor but are shadowed by other parts of the target, by learning to recognize the relative position among the points. The characteristics of this network also facilitated the training on images where the satellite was not entirely present, allowing to represent features outside the FOV through the pair of values (0,0); during inference, such features, whose regression cannot be performed correctly, are indicated with at least one coordinate equal to 0 or 1 and are excluded from the computation of the pose solution. The output of the network is therefore composed of the set of coordinates (u, v) of 11 target keypoints on the image plane of the cropped image; successively, the coordinates are restored to the original size of the input image before being fed to the pose estimation algorithm. It is worth noting that the network provides a fixed-size output, composed of the estimated position of all the 11 keypoints in the image; however, as previously mentioned, the detection of keypoints outside the FOV is not performed reliably by the network. Since, during inference, the coordinates are provided in the same order as for the training phase, the matching between the 3D and 2D coordinates is intrinsically achieved. Given the resulting set of 3D-2D point correspondences, the pose is estimated without requiring an initial guess in three steps: a coarse initial guess is obtained using the EPnP algorithm [25], which is followed by a numerical least squares solver for pose refinement based on the Gauss-Newton iterative algorithm [26], and by a final refinement based on the LM algorithm [27], a nonlinear optimization method that minimizes the error function between the projected 3D points (according to the estimated pose) and the observed 2D points in the image.

3 Results

3.1 CNN Training and Validation

The two CNNs composing the proposed monocular-based pose estimation pipeline were trained on the public dataset SPEED+ comprising 59,960 synthetic images and 9,531 real images captured within the Stanford’s Space Rendezvous Lab. Only the synthetic images (greyscale with a resolution of 1920x1200 pixels) are provided with true pose labels. So, for the activities conducted in this work, these images are randomly split into three subsets for training (80%) validation (15%) and testing (5%). CNNs training was performed through Kaggle GPU Kernels. Specifically, YOLOv8n ODN was trained over 40 epochs with a batch size of 32 images; the Adam algorithm with weight decay [28] was employed for weights’ optimization, with a momentum of 0.937 and a weight decay of 0.0005, and employing an automatic optimizer to dynamically adjust the learning rate, which decreases from 0.009503 to 0.000595. For YOLOv8s-pose, the training was extended to 120 epochs, employing a momentum of 0.937 and a weight decay of 0.0005 with a batch size of 16 images. The first 90 epochs used an automated optimization algorithm in which the learning rate decreases from 0.009009 to 0.000218, followed by 30 epochs using Stochastic Gradient Descent and a linear variation of the learning rate for fine-tuning. The training was concluded when a plateau on a low value of the loss function, computed on the validation subset, was reached. Small discrepancies between the components of the training and validation loss function were observed at the end of the training, thus demonstrating the generalization capability of the proposed models.

3.2 Performance Metrics

Object detection accuracy is measured by the well-known Intersection over Union (IoU) metric; in addition, the average distance between the center of the

predicted 2D bounding box and the ground truth 2D bounding box δ , in pixels, is provided. The pose estimation accuracy is evaluated using two distinct metrics E_R and E_T for rotational and translational errors, respectively. They are defined as follows,

$$E_R = 2 \cdot \arccos(|z|) \quad , \quad E_T = \|t^* - t\| \quad (3)$$

where z is the real part of the Hamilton product between the true (q^*) and the conjugate of the predicted (q) quaternion corresponding to the rotation matrix from camera to target reference frame, while t^* and t are the true and predicted position vectors of the target with respect to the camera. In addition, it is possible to define another metric, here called S_T which represents the relative position error scaled with respect to the true relative distance, as shown in the following equation:

$$S_T = \frac{\|t^* - t\|}{\|t^*\|} \quad (4)$$

Finally, an overall pose accuracy score is computed using the definition employed in the KSPEC as shown below,

$$\text{Score} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{E_T^{(i)}}{t^{(i)}} + E_R^{(i)} \cdot \frac{\pi}{180} \right) \quad (5)$$

where the position metric E_T is divided by the true relative distance to be dimensionless and E_R is converted in radians, while N is the number of images in the test set.

3.3 Testing Results

Table 1 shows the synthetic performance metrics of both the ODN and the KRN. The mean and median values of the IoU are particularly similar and this suggests the absence of outliers in the testing data. This hypothesis is confirmed by Figure 2, which shows a histogram depicting the probability distribution of IoU values. The results in Table 1 and Figure 3 show that the center position is estimated with a mean error of about 3 pixels and a standard deviation (std) of less than 5 pixels. Regarding the KRN, the prediction error in the keypoints' image coordinates (ϕ) has a mean of 7.07 pixels and a standard deviation of 8.27 pixels. In this case, the median value (4.6 pixels) differs from the mean, which suggests that outliers are present in images with high levels of darkness and in images where the satellite is not fully visible. Nevertheless, the overall pose estimation results collected in Table 2 show an average angular error of 1.37° and an average position error of about 4.7 cm. The standard deviations are equal to 1.22° and 4.3 cm respectively, confirming the presence of a small number of

outliers. Moreover, in 80% of the test images, the rotation error is less than 1.7° and the translation error is less than 7cm, which confirms the functionality of the architecture. Regarding the KSPEC score, the overall score of the proposed method on the testing dataset is equal to 0.0351. To avoid altering the performance metrics, they are evaluated by excluding three images for which the pose estimation is unsuccessful from the statistics. In Figure 4 one of the three cases is represented. In these worst cases, the projections of the four keypoints on the face of the solar panel and those on the other side of the spacecraft lead to an ambiguous pose solution, since the same projections may be associated with two different pose vectors, thus making the solver unable to discriminate the correct one. However, the erroneous pose estimate is characterized by a negative component of the relative position vector along the camera boresight axis. Since this condition is not compatible with the presence of the target in the camera FOV, this failure can be detected, leading to the discard of the pose solution before the error is injected into the relative navigation architecture. Moreover, such a problem could be solved when tracking the pose through a sequence of images exploiting the pose parameters knowledge at the previous frame.

Figure 2: Probability distribution of IoU values.

	IoU	$\delta(pixel)$	$\phi(pixel)$
Mean	0.98	3.33	7.07
Median	0.98	2.19	4.68
Std	0.01	4.61	8.27

Table 1: Object Detection and Keypoints Regression Results.

In Figure 4 one of the three cases is represented. In these worst cases, the projections of the four keypoints on the face of the solar panel and those on the other side of the spacecraft lead to an ambiguous pose solution, since the same projections may be associ-

Figure 3: Probability distribution of δ .

Metrics	Our Method
(Mean; Median; Std) E_R ($^\circ$)	(1.37; 1.09; 1.22)
(Mean; Median; Std) E_T (cm)	(4.7; 3.3; 4.3)
(Mean; Median; Std) S_T	(0.008; 0.006; 0.010)
Mean $ t^* - t $ (m)	[0.004 0.005 0.052]
Median $ t^* - t $ (m)	[0.003 0.004 0.039]
Std $ t^* - t $ (m)	[0.005 0.005 0.052]

Table 2: Metrics for the proposed method.

ated with two different pose vectors, thus making the solver unable to discriminate the correct one. However, the erroneous pose estimate is characterized by a negative component of the relative position vector along the camera boresight axis. Since this condition is not compatible with the presence of the target in the camera FOV, this failure can be detected, leading to the discard of the pose solution before the error is injected into the relative navigation architecture. Moreover, such a problem could be solved when tracking the pose through a sequence of images exploiting the pose parameters knowledge at the previous frame.

Figure 4: Critical Image for the Pose Solver.

4 Discussion

An original monocular-based pose estimation architecture for uncooperative satellites was presented. The architecture exploits two CNNs of the YOLOv8 family to perform object detection and keypoints’ regression, followed by a pose solver which is composed of the analytical EPnP algorithm with a Gauss-Newton optimization and a subsequent numerical refinement with the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm. The algorithmic pipeline, trained and tested on different subsets of synthetic images within the SPEED+ dataset, has proven the capability to estimate relative position with mm-level errors in the cross-boresight components and cm-level errors in the along boresight one, while relative attitude is determined with degree-level errors. Such promising performance suggests deepening the investigation of YOLOv8-based architectures since the achieved accuracy is very close to the one obtained by the most accurate state-of-the-art solutions [29] despite relying on a much smaller number of parameters. Specifically, the CNNs employed in this work require a total number of 14.8 million parameters, which is below the average number used by most state-of-the-art works. Indeed, many architectures use neural networks such as ResNet [30] and its variants like ResNet-50 and ResNet-101, which require a greater number of parameters and network depth; other solutions such as Faster R-CNN [17] can be heavier than YOLO due to their two-stage approach, requiring more computational resources. The lower number of parameters makes this solution particularly useful in space applications with limited processing resources of on-board satellite computers. Future works will address (i) testing on SPEED+ real images, (ii) further analyses varying network hyperparameters to find an optimal training configuration, (iii) integrating outliers rejection schemes in the pose solver step to improve robustness, and (iv) testing the pose estimation pipeline on a sequence of consecutive frames, to investigate its performance during pose tracking. Regarding the first upcoming activity, Lightbox and Sunlamp images from the SPEED+ dataset will be employed to conduct a comprehensive comparison with all the architectures that took part in KSPEC 2021. Finally, testing the method on real images will also allow assessing the effect of further dataset augmentation on the ability to operate with real images and reduce the vulnerability to the domain gap problem.

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